

Human Resurrection Project

Can science resurrect the dead using information extracted from DNA?

Abstract

DNA and information combined with science and biotechnology. Can we resurrect the dead?

Body

In a science fiction movie set in the 23rd century, scientists were able to “recreate” a deceased human being, using only the information extracted from his/her DNA. With that information at their disposal, they were able to bring him back to life using biotechnology. The process is pure science-fiction and the idea of bringing back to life a deceased person can only be considered as something utopian. The question remains: can we ever resurrect the dead?

Conclusion

Although the process is a science fiction fantasy, the tendency of these ideas getting fulfilled is very likely with the advances of science and biotechnology.

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